

Three-Term Linear Fractional Nabla Difference Equation

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ABSTRACT

In this present paper, a study on nabla difference equation and its third order linear fractional difference equation. A new generalized nabla difference equation is investigated from Three-term linear fractional nabla difference equation. A relevant example is proved and justify the proposed notions.

Keywords: Fractional difference operator, nabla difference equation, linear fractional, Third-term equation.

1. Introduction

In this present paper, we shall use the transform method to obtain solutions of a linear fractional nabla difference equation of the form

$$(1) \quad \nabla_0^\nu x(t) + C_1 \nabla x(t) + C_2 x(t) = g(t), \\ t = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Where $1 < \nu \leq 2$. The fractional difference operator, ∇_0^ν is of R-L type and the operator ∇_0^ν is a Riemann-Liouville fractional difference operator, is defined by,

If $\mu > 0$, define the μ^{th} -term of fractional sum by

$$(2) \quad \nabla_a^{-\mu} x(t) = \sum_{s=a}^t \frac{(t-\rho(s))^{\overline{\mu-1}}}{\Gamma \mu} x(s)$$

Where $\rho(s) = s - 1$.

The aim for this paper is to develop and preserve the theory of linear fractional nabla difference equations as a corresponds of the theory of linear difference

equations. We shall consider the three term equations, (1) is limited. An equation of the form

$$(3) \quad \nabla_0^{2\mu} x(t) + C_1 \nabla_0^\mu x(t) + C_2 x(t) = g(t), \\ t = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

is called a sequential fractional difference equation.

In general equation is,

$$(4) \quad \nabla_0^{\nu_2} x(t) + C_1 \nabla_0^{\nu_1} x(t) + C_2 x(t) = g(t), \\ t = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

Assume that $0 < \nu_1 \leq 1 < \nu_2 \leq 2$ as the only connection between ν_1 and ν_2 . The operator of nabla is usually represents the backward difference operator and in this paper

$$(5) \quad \nabla x(t) = x(t) - x(t-1),$$

$$\nabla^k x(t) = \nabla \nabla^{k-1} x(t), \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

The raising factorial power function is defined below,

$$(6) \quad t^{\overline{\alpha}} = \frac{\Gamma(t+\alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha)}.$$

Then if $0 \leq m-1 < \nu \leq m$, define by the Riemann-Liouville fractional difference equation is

$$(7) \quad \nabla_c^\nu x(t) = \nabla^m \nabla_c^{\nu-m} x(t)$$

Where ∇^m denotes the standard m^{th} order nabla (backward) difference.

In section 2, we shall use the transform method to (1) and we find out the solutions. And the same time we shall expressed as a sufficient condition as a function of C_1 and C_2 for convergent of the solutions.

In section 3, we apply the algorithm in the case of a solution is 2^t and verified independently that the series represents the known function.

For further studying in this previous area, we refer the reader to the article on two-term linear fractional nabla difference equation [7].

2. Three-term Linear fractional nabla difference equation

In this section, we describe an algorithm to form a solution of an initial value problem for a three-term linear fractional nabla difference equation of the form,

$$(8) \quad \nabla_0^\nu x(t) + C_1 \nabla x(t) + C_2 x(t) = 0, \quad x(0) = c_0, \\ x(1) = c_1 \quad \text{for } t = 1, 2, 3 \dots$$

Where $1 < \nu \leq 2$.

Apply the operator N_2 to the equation (8) we get,

$$N_2(\nabla_0^\nu x(t) + C_1 \nabla x(t) + C_2 x(t)) = 0$$

$$(9) \quad N_2(\nabla_0^\nu x(t)) + C_1 N_2(\nabla x(t)) + C_2 N_2 x(t) = 0$$

First, consider a term $N_2(\nabla_0^\nu x(t))$ from (8) and use the result [7] we get,

“If $1 < \nu \leq 2$,

$$N_{a+2}(\nabla_a^\nu f(t))(s) = s^\nu N_a(f(t))(s) \\ -s(1-s)^{a-1} f(a) - (1-s)^a \nabla_a^{\nu-1} f(a+1) \\ = s^\nu N_a(f(t))(s) - s(1-s)^{a-1} f(a) \\ -(1-s)^a (f(a+1) - (\nu-1)f(a)).”$$

Which implies that,

$$N_2(\nabla_0^\nu x(t)) = s^\nu N_0(x(t)) - s(1-s)^{0-1} x(0) \\ -(1-s)^0 (x(1) - (\nu-1)x(0))$$

$$(10) \quad N_2(\nabla_0^\nu x(t)) = s^\nu N_0(x(t)) \\ -s(1-s)^{-1} c_0 - (c_1 - (\nu-1)c_0)$$

Next, consider the term $N_2(\nabla x(t))$ on (9) and also, we know that the result [7],

$$“\text{If } 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad N_{a+1}(\nabla_a^\nu f(t))(s) = s^\nu N_a(f(t))(s) \\ -(1-s)^{a-1} f(a).”$$

Which implies

$$N_2(\nabla x(t)) = N_2(\nabla x(t)) + \nabla x(1) - \nabla x(1) \\ = N_1(\nabla x(t)) - \nabla x(1) \\ = sN_1(x(t)) - (1-s)^{-1} c_0 - (c_1 - c_0) \\ = sN_0(x(t)) - \frac{1}{(1-s)} c_0 - c_1 + c_0 \frac{(1-s)}{(1-s)} \\ = sN_0(x(t)) - \frac{1}{(1-s)} c_0 - c_1 + \frac{1}{(1-s)} c_0 - \frac{s}{(1-s)} c_0 \\ (11) \quad N_2(\nabla x(t)) = sN_0(x(t)) - \frac{s}{(1-s)} c_0 - c_1$$

Similarly, we consider the last term,

$$N_2(x(t)) = N_2(x(t)) + c_1 - c_1 + \frac{1}{(1-s)} c_0 - \frac{1}{(1-s)} c_0 \\ = N_2(x(t)) + c_1 + (1-s)^{-1} c_0 - c_1 + (1-s)^{-1} c_0$$

In particular

$$(12) \quad N_2(x(t)) = N_0(x(t)) - c_1 - (1-s)^{-1} c_0$$

Substitute (10), (11) and (12) in (9) we get

$$N_2(\nabla_0^\nu x(t)) + C_1 N_2(\nabla x(t)) + C_2 N_2 x(t) = 0 \\ s^\nu N_0(x(t)) - s(1-s)^{-1} c_0 - (c_1 - (\nu-1)c_0) \\ + C_1 \left(sN_0(x(t)) - \frac{s}{(1-s)} c_0 - c_1 \right) \\ + C_2 (N_0(x(t)) - c_1 - (1-s)^{-1} c_0) = 0$$

$$(s^\nu + C_1 s + C_2) N_0(x(t)) - \frac{1}{(1-s)} (s + C_1 s + C_2) c_0 \\ -(1 + C_1 + C_2) c_1 - (1-\nu) c_0 = 0$$

$$(13) N_0(x(t)) = \frac{(s + C_1s + C_2)c_0}{(1-s)(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} + \frac{(1 + C_1 + C_2)c_1 + (1-\nu)c_0}{(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)}$$

Now take $\frac{1}{(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} = \frac{1}{s^\nu \left(1 + \frac{C_1s}{s^\nu} + \frac{C_2}{s^\nu}\right)}$
 $= \frac{1}{s^\nu \left(1 + C_1s^{1-\nu} + \frac{C_2}{s^\nu}\right)}$

$$\frac{1}{(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} = \frac{1}{s^\nu (1 + C_1s^{1-\nu})} \ln \left(1 + \frac{C_2}{s^\nu (1 + C_1s^{1-\nu})}\right)$$

general,

$$\frac{1}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n s^{-\nu(n+1)} C_2^n \left(\frac{1}{1 + C_1s^{1-\nu}}\right)^{n+1}$$

Note that,

$$\left(\frac{1}{1 + C_1s^{1-\nu}}\right)^{n+1} = \sum_{m=n}^{\infty} (-1)^{m+n} \binom{m}{n} (C_1s^{1-\nu})^{m-n}$$

We get

$$\frac{1}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=n}^{\infty} (-1)^m \binom{m}{n} C_1^{m-n} s^{(1-\nu)m-n} C_2^n s^{-\nu(n+1)}$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m \binom{m}{n} C_1^{m-n} C_2^n s^{m-m\nu-n+\nu n-\nu}$$

$$(14) \frac{1}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m \binom{m}{n} C_1^{m-n} C_2^n s^{((1-\nu)m-n-\nu)}$$

Since $s^{((1-\nu)m-n-\nu)} = N_1 \left(\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}\right)$
 $= N_0 \left(\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}\right)$.

By using the result [7], “

$$AN_1f(t) = -\frac{Af(0)}{1-s} + AN_0f(t)”.$$

Now, the above equation is re-express N_1 as N_0 , and we have,

$$\frac{1}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m \binom{m}{n} C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \left(N_1 \left(\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}\right)\right)$$

$$(15) = N_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \left(\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}\right)$$

It follows from the result [7]

$$“N_a f(t+1) = (1-s)^{-1} N_{a+1} f(t)”.$$

Which implies that, equation (15) we get,

$$\frac{(1-s)^{-1}}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = N_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \left(\frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}\right)$$

$$(16)$$

Moreover, from (14)

$$\frac{1}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m \binom{m}{n} C_1^{m-n} C_2^n s^{(1-\nu)m-n-\nu} \cdot \frac{s}{s}$$

$$\frac{s}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m \binom{m}{n} C_1^{m-n} C_2^n s^{(1-\nu)m-n-\nu+1}$$

Similarly, we get

$$\frac{s}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} N_0$$

$$\left(\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \right)$$

and so

$$\frac{s(1-s)^{-1}}{s^\nu + C_1s + C_2} = N_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n}$$

$$(17) \left(\frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \right)$$

We consider an equation (13) we get

$$\begin{aligned} N_0x(t) &= \frac{(s + C_1s + C_2)c_0}{(1-s)(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} \\ &+ \frac{(1 + C_1 + C_2)c_1 + (1 - \nu)c_0}{(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} \\ (18) \quad N_0x(t) &= \frac{C_2c_0}{(1-s)(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} \\ &+ \frac{s(1 + C_1)c_0}{(1-s)(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} \\ &+ \frac{(1 + C_1 + C_2)c_1 + (1 - \nu)c_0}{(s^\nu + C_1s + C_2)} \end{aligned}$$

Substitute (15), (16) and (17) directly into (18) we get

$$\begin{aligned} N_0x(t) &= C_2c_0N_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \\ &+ (1+C_1)c_0N_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \\ &+ KN_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \end{aligned}$$

$$x(t) = C_2c_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))}$$

$$+ (1+C_1)c_0 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))}$$

$$+ K \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))}$$

(19)

Where $K = ((1 + C_1 + C_2)c_1 + (1 - \nu)c_0)$.

To simplify this representation, note that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} &= \frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \\ &+ \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} &= \frac{\Gamma(t+1+(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \\ &= t \frac{\Gamma(t+(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \\ &+ ((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)) \frac{\Gamma(t+(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, (19) can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= K_1 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \\ &+ K_2 \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$(21) \quad K_1 = c_0(1 + C_1 + C_2),$$

$K_2 = K + c_0C_2 = (1 + C_1 + C_2)c_1 + (1 - \nu + C_2)c_0$ Note that

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-2)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} \quad (22)$$

and

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m (-1)^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)} \tag{23}$$

are two linear independent solutions of (8). We give the details to obtain conditions for absolute convergence in (23) for fixed t .

First note that for each $t \geq 1$, $\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}$ is an increasing function in n . Now consider the ratio $\frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+1+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+1+\nu)} / \frac{t^{(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}}{\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}$

Then

$$\frac{\Gamma(t+(\nu-1)m+n+1+(\nu-1))}{\Gamma(t)\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+1+\nu)} \frac{\Gamma(t)\Gamma((\nu-1)m+n+\nu)}{\Gamma(t+(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1))} = \frac{t+(\nu-1)m+n+(\nu-1)}{(\nu-1)m+n+\nu} \geq 1$$

and the inequality is strict if $t > 1$.

Thus, compare (23) to

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^{(\nu m+(\nu-1))}}{\Gamma(\nu m+\nu)} \left| \sum_{n=0}^m C_1^{m-n} C_2^n \binom{m}{n} \right| = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(t)^{(\nu m+(\nu-1))}}{\Gamma(\nu m+\nu)} |C_1 + C_2|^m$$

and apply the ratio test. Thus, each of (22) and (23) are absolutely convergent if $|C_1 + C_2| < 1$.

Description of known functions:

We represent this method with an initial value problem for a classical second order finite difference equation. The unique solution of the initial value problem is $x(t) = 2^t$, thus we obtain a series representation of 2^t as a linear combination of the forms (22) and (23).

Consider the initial value problem

$$(24) \quad 10\nabla^2 x(t) - \nabla x(t) - 2x(t) = 0, \quad t = 2, 3, \dots, \\ x(0) = 1, x(1) = 2.$$

Then, apply (13) with

$$C_1 = \frac{-1}{10}, \quad C_2 = \frac{-1}{5}, \quad c_0 = 1, \quad c_1 = 2, \\ \nu = 2,$$

To obtain

$$N_0 x(t) = \frac{(s + (-1/10)s + (-1/5))1}{(1-s)(s^2 + (-1/10)s + (-1/5))} + \frac{(1 + (-1/10) + (-1/5))2 + (1-2)1}{(s^2 + (-1/10)s + (-1/5))} \\ N_0 x(t) = \frac{s - \frac{1}{10}s - \frac{1}{5}}{(1-s)\left(s^2 - \frac{1}{10}s - \frac{1}{5}\right)} + \frac{2 - \frac{2}{10} - \frac{2}{5} - 1}{\left(s^2 - \frac{1}{10}s - \frac{1}{5}\right)} \\ N_0 x(t) = \frac{\frac{9}{10}s - \frac{1}{5}}{(1-s)\left(s^2 - \frac{1}{10}s - \frac{1}{5}\right)} + \frac{\frac{4}{10}}{\left(s^2 - \frac{1}{10}s - \frac{1}{5}\right)}$$

From (21), $K_1 = 1 \left(1 - \frac{1}{10} - \frac{1}{5}\right) = \frac{7}{10}$

$$K_2 = \left(1 - \frac{1}{10} - \frac{1}{5}\right)2 + \left(1 - 2 - \frac{1}{5}\right)1 = \left(\frac{7}{10}\right)2 - \frac{6}{5} = \frac{1}{5}$$

and

$$x(t) = \frac{7}{10} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)} + \frac{1}{5} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t)^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+2)}.$$

(25)

The unique solution of (24) is 2^t and the series given in (25) absolutely convergent for all $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Write

$$(25) \text{ as } x(t) = \frac{7}{10} C(t) + \frac{1}{5} D(t).$$

Where $C(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t+1)^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)}$

$$D(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{(t)^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

To prove $x(t+1) = 2x(t)$, or

$$\frac{7}{10}C(t+1) + \frac{1}{5}D(t+1) = 2\left(\frac{7}{10}C(t) + \frac{1}{5}D(t)\right)$$

It is sufficient to show that

$$D(t+1) = C(t) + D(t) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{7}{10}C(t+1) = \left(\frac{6}{5}C(t) + \frac{1}{5}D(t)\right).$$

Now consider $D(t+1)$,

$$D(t+1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n+1}}}{\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{\Gamma(t+1+m+n+1)}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} (t+m+n+1) \frac{\Gamma(t+m+n+1)}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} t \frac{\Gamma(t+m+n+1)}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$+ \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} (m+n+1) \frac{\Gamma(t+m+n+1)}{\Gamma(t+1)\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$D(t+1) = D(t) + C(t).$$

We have yet to obtain a direct approach to take $C(t+1)$. We begin by showing directly that $D(t)$ satisfies

$$10\nabla^2 x(t) - \nabla x(t) - 2x(t) = 0, \quad t = 2, 3, \dots$$

Apply the power rule and

$$D(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n+1}}}{\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$\nabla D(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)}$$

$$\nabla^2 D(t) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n-1}}}{\Gamma(m+n)}$$

Thus,

$$\nabla^2 D(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{m+1} \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m+1-n} \binom{m+1}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)}$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^m \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \left(\binom{m}{n} + \binom{m}{n-1} \right) \frac{t^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)}$$

$$+ \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^{m+1} \frac{t^{\overline{2m+1}}}{\Gamma(2m+2)}$$

$$= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{10} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)}$$

$$+ \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{m+1} \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n-1} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n}}}{\Gamma(m+n+1)}$$

$$= \frac{1}{10} \nabla D(t) + \frac{1}{5} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^m \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^n \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{m-n} \binom{m}{n} \frac{t^{\overline{m+n+1}}}{\Gamma(m+n+2)}$$

$$\nabla^2 D(t) = \frac{1}{10} \nabla D(t) + \frac{1}{5} D(t)$$

A similar calculation shows that $C(t)$ satisfies

$$10\nabla^2 x(t) - \nabla x(t) - 2x(t) = 0, \quad t = 2, 3, \dots$$

We close by arguing that

$$\frac{7}{10}C(t+1) = \left(\frac{6}{5}C(t) + \frac{1}{5}D(t)\right).$$

Simplify

$$10\nabla^2 C(t+1) - \nabla C(t+1) - 2C(t+1) = 0$$

$$10(C(t+1) - 2C(t) + C(t-1)) - (C(t+1) - C(t)) - 2C(t+1) = 0$$

To obtain $\frac{7}{10}C(t+1) = \frac{19}{10}C(t) - C(t-1)$

$$= \frac{6}{5}C(t) + \left(\frac{7}{10}C(t) - C(t-1)\right)$$

Now it is sufficient to show that

$$\left(\frac{7}{10}C(t) - C(t-1)\right) = \frac{1}{5}D(t).$$

Employ $C(t) = D(t+1) - D(t)$ and

$C(t-1) = D(t) - D(t-1)$ to obtain

$$\left(\frac{7}{10}C(t) - C(t-1)\right) = \frac{7}{10}(D(t+1)$$

$$-D(t)) - (D(t) - D(t-1))$$

$$= \frac{7}{10}(D(t+1) - \frac{17}{10}D(t) + D(t-1))$$

$$= \left(\frac{7}{10}(D(t+1) - \frac{19}{10}D(t) + D(t-1))\right) + \frac{2}{10}D(t)$$

$$\left(\frac{7}{10}C(t) - C(t-1)\right) = \frac{1}{5}D(t).$$

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